
Managing Stress by Music Therapy

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Abstract:

Stress Management is a wide spectrum of techniques and psychotherapies aimed at controlling a person's level of stress, especially chronic stress, usually for the purpose of and for the motive of improving everyday functioning. Music therapy is the use of music to address the physical, emotional, cognitive, and social needs of a group or individual. It employs a variety of activities, such as listening to melodies, playing an instrument, drumming, writing songs, and guided imagery. Music therapy is appropriate for people of all ages, whether they are virtuosos or tone deaf, struggling with illnesses or totally healthy.

Music therapy touches all aspects of the mind, body, brain and behavior. Music can provide a distraction for the mind, it can slow the rhythms of the body, and it can alter our mood, which in turn can influence behavior. Music is effective for relaxation and stress management. If you want to take the positive effects of listening to music to another level, try singing. Singing is one of the best ways to shift the vibrations of our thoughts and the very cells of our body, helping slow and regulate breathing and promote relaxation.

This form of treatment may be helpful for people with depression and anxiety, and it may help improve the quality of life for people with physical health problems. Anyone can engage in music therapy; you don't need a background in music to experience its beneficial effects.

Thus, this paper makes an attempt to study the stress management through a unique way through a musical therapy.

Key Words: - *Stress management, Music Therapy, engaging in hobbies to reduce stress.*

Introduction:

1. Introduction to Stress and Stress Management Techniques:

Stress is our body's Response to pressure. Many Life events or varied situations can cause stress. It is often triggered when we experienced something new, unexpected or that threatens our sense of self, or when we have no or very little control over the situation.

Different people deal with stress differently. The ability to cope up with the stressors depends on number of factors, viz. early life events, personality and social and economic circumstances. Time stress, Anticipatory stress, Situational stress and Encounter stress are the four types of stress.

Stress management is a wide spectrum of techniques and psychotherapies aimed at controlling a person's level of stress, especially chronic stress, usually for the purpose of and for the motive of improving everyday functioning.

There are things we can learn to help us cope up with the stress before it gets to be too much. These tips may help us keep stress at bay:

- Keep a positive attitude.
- Accept that there are events that we cannot control.
- Be assertive instead of aggressive. Assert your feelings, opinions, or beliefs instead of becoming angry, defensive, or passive.
- Learn to manage our time more effectively.
- Set limits appropriately and say no to requests that would create excessive stress in our life.
- Make time for hobbies and interests.
- Don't rely on alcohol, drugs to reduce the stress. Drugs and alcohol can stress your body even more.
- Seek out social support. Spend enough time with loved ones.
- Seek treatment from the professional trainer to learn more healthy ways of dealing with the stress in our life.

2. Music Therapy:

Music therapy is the use of music to address the physical, emotional, cognitive, and social needs of a group or individual. It employs a variety of activities, such as listening to melodies, playing an instrument, drumming, writing songs, and guided imagery. Music therapy is appropriate for people of all ages, whether they are virtuosos or tone deaf, struggling with illnesses or totally healthy.

Music therapy touches all aspects of the mind, body, brain and behavior. Music can provide a distraction for the mind, it can slow the rhythms of the body, and it can alter our mood, which in turn can influence behavior.

There are many different approaches to music therapy, including creating music, listening to music, and talking about music. Although music therapy is often used to promote mental and emotional health, it may also help improve quality of life for people coping with physical health conditions.

Music can have a profound effect on both the emotions and the body. Faster music can make you feel more alert and concentrate better. Upbeat music can make you feel more optimistic and positive about life. A slower tempo can quiet your mind and relax your muscles, making you feel soothed while releasing the stress of the day. Music is effective for relaxation and stress management. If you want to take the positive effects of listening to music to another level, try singing. Singing is one of the best ways to shift the vibrations of our thoughts and the very cells of our body, helping slow and regulate breathing and promote relaxation. If you're going to sing, pick songs you know will put you in a better mood, inspire you, or help you relax. Pay attention to how different you feel after a few minutes of singing aloud, and make note of the songs that make you feel best so you can return to them when you need them most.

Music therapy is a therapeutic approach that uses the naturally mood-lifting properties of music to help people improve their mental health and overall well-being. It's a goal-oriented intervention that may involve:

- Making music
- Writing songs

Review of Literature:

Yadira Alborno (2010) music therapy on depression in adolescents and adults with substance abuse: a randomized controlled trial” The effect of group improvisational music therapy on depression in adolescents and adults with substance abuse was investigated. As for post-test measures, significant differences were found between the groups on HRSD but not the BDI. Among limitations of the study were: a small sample size and the absence of a depression assessment tool for substance abuse.

Bill Matne (2018) In their journal entitled “Understanding literature reviews: Implications for music therapy” The purpose of this article is to present a comprehensive overview of literature review processes and methodologies by (a) describing the general purposes of narrow and broad literature reviews, (b) providing a historical overview of broad reviews, and (c) describing broad review methodologies in relation to their respective definitions, histories, methodological characteristics, purposes, example questions, and study examples from healthcare and music therapy literature.

Loory F Gooding (2019) In their journal entitled, “Music Therapy with Military Populations: A Scoping Review” Current research on music therapy with military populations is growing, but more information is needed to inform practice in a field. This scoping review provides an up-to-date synthesis of the available information on the use of music therapy interventions to promote health and improve functioning in military service members.

Research Methodology:

1. Objectives:

1. To know the types, pros and cons of the music therapy.
2. To understand the effects of stress and ways to manage it
3. To know the techniques, activities and tools of music therapy.

2. Scope of Study:

The proposed study is to understand how the music therapy is used to manage and reduce the stress of the life. Music is one of the oldest and most popular way to manage stress and relax the body. It is very essential for the people to maintain the effective physical and mental health in order to contribute towards the productivity of an organisation. This paper tries to recommend the stress management with the help of musical therapy.

3. Limitations:

As the music therapy is still not that popular, it became difficult to collect the primary data.

4. Data Collection

Primary Data: Data has been collected by the researcher himself/herself through surveys, interviews with the help of specially designed questionnaire.

Secondary Data: Newspaper, Magazines, journals, Internet facilities, etc

Sample size: 52

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

What type of music do you like?

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Pop Music	28	53.8%
Jazz	14	26.9%
Hip Hop Music	24	46.2%
Classic Music	24	46.2%
Rock	24	46.2%
Folk Music	13	25%

The above table shows majority of people like Pop Music.

8. To what extent do you think the music treatment can lower your stress?

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Least 1	1	1.9%
2	2	3.8%
3	8	15.4%
4	15	28.8%
5Most	26	50%

The above diagram shows the how people extent their stress using music therapy the most is 50% and the least is 1.9%.

9. Which you are aware of the signs and symptoms of stress.

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Frequent headache or pains	32	61.5%
Trembling of lips and hands	23	44.2%
Heart palpitations or chest pain	24	46.2%
Cold or sweaty hands and feet	19	36.5%
Dry mouth	32	61.5%
Increased anger	27	51.9%
Aching shoulders, neck and back	17	32.7%

The above diagram shows us the Frequent headache or pains is 61.5%, Trembling of lips and hands is 44.2%, Heart palpitations or chest pain is 46.2%, Cold or sweaty hands and feet is 36.5%, Dry mouth is 61.5%, Increased anger is 51.9%, Aching shoulders, neck and back is 32.7%.

10. Which the listed music performances would serve as therapy for managing stress?

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Traditional Music	29	55.8%
Instrumental Music	22	42.3%
Classical Music	23	44.2%
Vocal Music	25	48.1%
Dance drama	28	53.8%
Juju Music	16	30.8%
Jazz	10	19.2%

In the above horizontal diagram shows the music performances serve as therapy for managing stress that is Traditional Music is 55.8%, Instrumental Music is 42.3%, Classical Music is 44.2%, Vocal Music is 48.1%, Dance drama is 53.8%, Juju Music is 30.8%, Jazz is 19.2%.

11. The hindrances to the use of music performance for stress management.

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of fund for carrying out the performances	32	61.5%
Lack of adequate staff training in performances	20	38.5%
High cost and maintenance of musical equipment's	39	75%
Lack of steady power supply	23	44.2%
Lack of interest on the part of lecturers	22	42.3%
Attitudes of those academics to music performances	23	44.2%

The above diagram shows the hindrances to use muse is Lack of fund for 38.5%, High cost and maintenance of musical equipment's is 75%, Lack of steady power supply is 44.2%, Lack of interest on the part of lecturers is 42.3%, Attitudes of those academics to music performances is 44.2%.

12. Strategies would help in stress management

52 responses

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Listening to melodious songs	21	40.4%
Attending to music performances	21	40.4%
Reading books on music performances	22	42.3%
Watching different music performances	31	59.6%
Playing some musical instruments	21	40.4%
Singing comfortable songs	33	63.5%
Dancing to music that appeals to you	16	30.8%

Listening to melodious songs is 40.4%, Attending to music performances is 40.4%, Reading books on music performances is 42.3%, Watching different music performances is 59.6%, Playing some musical instruments is 40.4%, Singing comfortable songs is 63.5%, Dancing to music that appeals to you is 30.8%.

15. Do you believe in the effectiveness of music as a therapy?

52 responses

Out of 52 respondents, 51 respondents i.e. 98.1% are sure that music is effective as a therapy and 1 respondent i.e. 1.9% is not sure about it.

Suggestions:

1. Experience a "sound bath" and let the music carry away.
2. Eat and drink to optimize the health.
3. Aerobic exercise has been shown to release endorphins—natural substances that help to feel better and maintain a positive attitude.
4. Stop using tobacco and nicotine products.
5. To examine the values and live by them.
6. Set realistic goals and expectations. Be mindful of the things that can control and work on accepting the things that we can't control.
7. When you're feeling overwhelmed, remind yourself of what you do well. Have a healthy sense of self-esteem.

8. You can use to relax or reduce stress, including
 - Deep breathing exercises.
 - Meditation.
 - Mindfulness meditation.
 - Progressive muscle relaxation.
 - Mental imagery relaxation.
 - Relaxation to music.
 - Biofeedback
 - Counselling, to help you recognize and release stress.
9. Working out regularly is one of the best ways to relax your body and mind. Plus, exercise will improve your mood.
10. When you're stressed, your muscles get tense. You can help loosen them up on your own and refresh your body by:
 - Stretching
 - Enjoying a massage
 - Taking a hot bath or shower
 - Getting a good night's sleep
11. Relaxing hobbies include things like:
 - Reading
 - Knitting
 - Doing an art project
 - Playing golf
 - Watching a movie
 - Doing puzzles
 - Playing cards and board games
12. Guided meditation is a great way to distract yourself from the stress of day

Conclusion:

Our findings indicate that music listening impacted the psychobiological stress system. Listening to music prior to a standardized stressor predominantly affected the autonomic nervous system (in terms of a faster recovery), and to a lesser degree the endocrine and psychological stress response. These findings may help better understanding the beneficial effects of music on the human body.

It is concluded that music therapy can be effectively used to overcome and prevent stress, depression and anxiety related disorders if used regularly in a prescribed manner under a supervision of a music therapist. It has a potential to be used in preventive as well as curative healthcare as an adjunct therapy. In depth research is on way to quantify the effect music has on brain functioning.

References:

1. Sonja Aalbers Annemieke Vink Ruth E. Freeman Kim Pattiselanno Marinus Spreen Susan van Hooren, 2019, Development of an improvisational music therapy intervention for young adults with depressive symptoms: An intervention mapping study, *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, Volume 65, PP-1-11
2. Genevieve Beaulieu-Boire, Solange Bourque, Frederic Chagnon, Lucie Chouinard, Nicole Gallo-Payet, Olivier Lesur, 2013, Music and biological stress dampening in mechanically-ventilated patients at the intensive care unit ward-a prospective interventional randomized

crossover trial, National Center for Biotechnology Information

3. Linda Chlan, 1998, Effectiveness of a music therapy intervention on relaxation and anxiety for patients receiving ventilatory assistance, *Heart & Lung*, Issue 3, Volume 27, PP-169-176
4. Sangeetha Nayak, Barbara L Wheeler, Samuel C, Shifflett Sandra, 2000, Effect of Musical Therapy on Mood and Social Interaction among Individuals with Acute Traumatic Brain Injury and Stroke, Volume 45, PP 274-283
5. Yadira Albornoz, 2010, effects of group improvisational music therapy on depression in adolescents and adults with substance abuse: a randomized controlled trial, *Nordic Journal of Music Therapy*, Volume 20, PP-208-224
6. Bittman BB, Berk LS, Felton DL, Westgard J, Simonton OC, Pappas J, Nine Houser M, 2001, Composite effects of group drumming music therapy on modulation of neuroendocrine- immune parameters in normal subjects, *ALTERNATIVE THERAPIES IN HEALTH AND MEDICINE*, Volume-7, PP- 38-47
7. Lori F Gooding, Diane G Langston ,2019, Music Therapy with Military Populations: A Scoping Review, *Journal of Music Therapy*, Volume 56, PP- 315–347
8. Orii McDermott, Nadia Crellin, Ridder, Martin, 2012, Music therapy in dementia: a narrative synthesis systematic review, *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, Volume 28, Issue 8, PP-781-794
9. Bill Matney, 2018, Understanding literature reviews: Implications for music therapy, *Nordic Journal of Music Therapy*, Volume 27, PP- 97-12